

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF MANGANESE (III) WITH BIGUANIDES

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Some stable cationic chelate complexes of tripositive manganese with biguanide and ethylenedibiguanide have been isolated and studied. A particularly interesting feature of these complexes is indicated by the fact that in them the manganese atom is co-ordinated with nitrogen atoms of the ligand molecules, instance of which is not found in the literature as yet. Furthermore, barring the single instance of bis-acetylacetonate-diaquo manganese (III), the compounds described in this paper represent the only well-defined series of some cationic complexes of tripositive manganese.

$[(OH)(H_2O)Mn^{III}(Big)_2]$ (where Big H is a molecule of biguanide), presumed to be the initial product of reaction, forms in vacuum a diol binuclear complex of the type (1).

The latter becomes anhydrous at 90° without any decomposition. Its effective moment value of $4.7 \mu_B$ suggests the presence of outer-level sp^3d^2 hybrid bonds or ion-dipole bonds. The ethylenedibiguanide complex, $[(OH)(H_2O)Mn^{III}Et(Big)_2]$, which forms dark chocolate-red crystals, is stable even up to 110° . In view of its low moment value of $3.26 \mu_B$, it may be regarded as a penetration complex with d^3sp^3 bonds with some imperfectly quenched orbital moment. In faintly acid solutions, a diaquo complex cation is formed, which has been isolated as a series of its salts having the composition, $[(H_2O)_2Mn^{III}Et(BigH)_2]X_2$, where $X = \frac{1}{2}(SO_4)$, $\frac{1}{2}(SeO_4)$ and $\frac{1}{2}(CrO_4)$. They form yellow to yellowish brown silky crystals. These, however, show effective moment values of $4.58 \mu_B$, characteristic of Mn^{3+} ion. These salts therefore represent associated or outer-level complexes with sp^3d^2 hybrid bonds resonating with ionic ones. Both the hydroxo-aquo and diaquo complexes possess presumably the *trans*-structure in view of the fact that the quadridentate ethylenedibiguanide ligand tends preferably to assume a planar orientation around the central metal atom.

Biguanide and its substituted derivatives have been shown by Rây and co-workers (*this Journal*) to possess remarkable capacity for co-ordination with transitional metal atoms, giving rise to extraordinarily stable inner-level or penetration complexes. Previous investigations were concerned mainly with Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Pd^{II} , Co^{III} , Cr^{III} and Ag^{III} . The silver ethylenedibiguanide serves indeed as a unique instance of a cationic complex of the metal in the tripositive state. The present investigation deals with a study of the preparation and properties of some similar stable cationic complexes of biguanide and ethylenedibiguanide with tri- and tetrapositive manganese.

Tervalent manganese, owing partly to its comparatively high electronegativity, has a more or less pronounced tendency to form complexes in which its valency stage is stabilised. The electronic configuration of the manganic ion, with four $3d$ electrons is, on the basis of Pauling's theory, also favourable for the formation of hybrid covalent bonds. That so far only a few such complexes have been prepared, might be ascribed to the ease with which the Mn^{3+} ion hydrolyses with the precipitation of Mn_2O_3 or its hydrates.

Tripositive manganese mostly forms complexes of the ionic type with ligands of high electronegativity containing oxygen as the donor atom, such as, oxalic acid, malonic acid, salicylic acid, sulphuric acid, phosphoric acid and iodic acid.

Complex fluoride, chloride and cyanide are also fairly known. Like many other tripositive ions, Mn^{III} forms neutral complexes with acetylacetonone and benzoyl-acetonone. The cationic complexes of tripositive manganese are on the other hand relatively scarce. The only instance of the type, reported lately, is furnished by bis-acetylacetonone-diaquo manganese^{III} salts isolated by Cartledge (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 6015) as the olive-green perchlorate and chloride. Moreover, manganese has been found to show little tendency to co-ordinate with nitrogen atom as donor.

It is therefore significant that manganese has been found to give rise to stable cationic chelate complexes in its tri- and tetrapositive states by co-ordinating with the nitrogen atoms of the biguanide ligands. An account of the preparation and properties of the tripositive complexes with biguanide and ethylenedibiguanide is given in the present paper. Those of the tetrapositive metal with the same ligands have been reported in a separate communication in this issue.

The complex manganese (III) biguanide has been prepared by the aerial oxidation of a mixture of an excess of biguanide sulphate and manganous sulphate in strongly alkaline medium. The same compound is also formed on treating freshly prepared manganic acetate with an alkaline solution of biguanide. It forms dark chocolate-coloured shining crystals, insoluble in water. The vacuum-dried sample corresponds to the composition, $[(Big)_2 Mn^{III} OH] \cdot 0.5 H_2O$, where $BigH$ is a molecule of biguanide. It is presumed that $[(OH)(H_2O)Mn^{III}(Big)_2]$ or its hydrate is the initial product of reaction, which in vacuum loses water, giving rise to a diol binuclear compound of the type (I).

At 90° the corresponding anhydrous compound is formed.

The complex manganese^{III} ethylenedibiguanide, $[(OH)(H_2O)Mn^{III}Et(Big)_2]$, where $Et(BigH)_2$ is a molecule of ethylenedibiguanide, has been prepared by the aerial oxidation of a mixture of ethylenedibiguanide sulphate and manganous sulphate in a strongly alkaline medium. It forms very stable dark chocolate-red crystals, sparingly soluble in water. The vacuum-dried sample, having the composition $[(OH)(H_2O)Mn^{III}Et(Big)_2] \cdot 0.5 H_2O$ loses 0.5 H_2O at 90°. In aqueous solution it suffers hydrolysis with the formation of a diaquo complex in equilibrium. The hydrolytic reaction is favoured by the presence of hydrogen ions, as is evident from the following representation :

A series of complex diaquo salts of the composition: $[(H_2O)_2Mn^{III}Et(BigH)_2]X_2$, where $X = \frac{1}{2}(SO_4)$, $\frac{1}{2}(SeO_4)$ and $\frac{1}{2}(CrO_4)$, has been isolated from the solution of the hydroxo-aquo base in acetic acid by the addition of the corresponding alkali salts.

These form yellow or yellowish brown silky crystals, almost insoluble in water. Both the hydroxo-aquo and the diaquo complexes possess presumably the *trans* structure in view of the fact that the quadridentate ethylenedibiguanide ligand tends preferably to give rise to a planar configuration around the central metal atom.

The effective magnetic moment values of these tripositive manganese biguanide complexes, as determined from their susceptibility measurements, are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Substance.	$\chi_g \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	* $D \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$ (corr.)	μ_B (effec.)
1. Diol-dimanganese <i>tetrakis</i> -biguanide	31.9	8963.9	+95.5	9059.4	4.70 (30°)
2. Hydroxo-aquo manganese ethylene- dibiguanide	12.68	4216.0	+132.2	4348.2	3.26 (30°)
3. Diaquo manganese ethylenedibiguanide sulphate	16.12	8333.0	+229.7	8562.7	4.57 (29.2°)
4. Diaquo manganese ethylenedibiguanide selenate	14.16	8320.0	+246.8	8566.8	4.58 (30°)

* D = diamagnetic correction.

It will be found that the compounds No. 1, 3 and 4 give moment values (4.6-4.7) more or less in agreement with the theoretical value of $4.9 \mu_B$ on the basis of spin-only effective formula for the associated or outer-level complexes of tripositive manganese with no electron pairing. On the other hand, the compound No. 2, hydroxo-aquo manganese^{III} ethylenedibiguanide, shows a much lower moment value of $3.26 \mu_B$, but somewhat higher than $2.82 \mu_B$, expected theoretically for a penetration or lower-level Mn^{III} complex in which electron pairing occurs with d^2sp^3 octahedral bonds. The difference might be attributed to the imperfect quenching of the orbital moment, contribution of which cannot therefore be altogether neglected (cf. Kotani, *J. Phys. Soc. Japan*, 1945, **4**, 293).

EXPERIMENTAL

Diol-di-Manganese^{III} *tetrakis-Biguanide Monohydrate*.—Biguanide acid sulphate (7 g.), dissolved in 8% NaOH solution (50 c.c.), was filtered by suction into a filter-flask, and to it a solution of MnSO₄·4H₂O (17 g. in 10 c.c. of water) was added with brisk shaking, when manganous hydroxide was precipitated. The filter-flask was closed with a bung, carrying an inlet tube reaching to the bottom of the flask, and a rapid current of air was drawn through the mixture for about 3 hours. The suspended manganous hydroxide was gradually converted into dark chocolate glistening crystals which accumulated at the bottom of the flask. After oxidation was completed (as indicated

by a clear orange-red supernatant liquid), the air current was stopped and the mixture was filtered by suction in a sintered glass crucible. The crystals on the filter-bed were washed several times with small portions of ice-cold water, sucked well and finally kept in vacuum over CaCl_2 and KOH ; yield 0.6-0.8 g.

The orange-red alkaline filtrate on being kept aside in air at room temperature deposited in a day or two shining red crystals analysing as $[(\text{OH})_2\text{Mn}^{\text{IV}}(\text{BigH})_2](\text{OH})_2$ (cf. this issue, p. 601).

The same tripositive manganese complex was also obtained by treating freshly prepared manganic acetate with an alkaline biguanide solution. Here also aerial oxidation led to the partial formation of the tetrapositive complex which remained in solution. [Found: Mn, 19.44; O(active), 2.83, 2.85; N, 50.67, 51.60. Formula of compound (I) requires Mn, 19.57; O(active), 2.85; N, 49.83%. Found (for the sample dehydrated at 90°): O(active), 2.95. Calc. for the dehydrated product: O(active), 2.94%].

The product forms dark chocolate-coloured shining crystals, insoluble in water. It loses its water of hydration at 90° without any decomposition and hydrolyses in contact with water, showing strongly alkaline reaction to litmus ($p_n > 8$). It dissolves in dilute acetic acid to a brown solution which readily becomes turbid with precipitation of hydrated Mn_2O_3 . A violet solution is obtained in syrupy phosphoric acid, characteristic of tripositive manganese compounds. A sample was found to remain unchanged when preserved for two months in vacuum over calcium chloride and caustic potash [O(active), 2.80%].

Hydroxo-aquo Manganese^{III} Ethylenedibiguanide.—Ethylenedibiguanide acid sulphate (5.4 g.), dissolved in 5% NaOH solution (60 c.c.), was filtered by suction into a filter-flask. It was then mixed with a solution of manganous sulphate (1.34 g. in 20 c.c. of water) when manganous hydroxide was precipitated. A brisk current of air was drawn through the mixture when the suspended manganous hydroxide gradually dissolved, giving a dark red solution. An almost clear solution was obtained within 15 to 20 minutes. Any insoluble matter was filtered off. A brisk current of air was passed through the filtrate again for about an hour in the cold. The crystals which separated were filtered by suction on a sintered glass-bed funnel, washed with ice-cold water and finally dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 and KOH ; yield 1.3-1.4 g. The dark red filtrate from above was kept aside for evaporation in air at room temperature, when a second crop of dark chocolate-red well-formed crystals separated from the solution. Unlike the case of simple biguanide, no further oxidation of tripositive manganese in the filtrate occurred here. {Found: Mn, 16.84; O(active), 2.46; N, 43.12. $[(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}\text{Et}(\text{Big})_2] \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 16.92; O(active), 2.46; N, 43.07% }.

The substance on being heated at 90° becomes anhydrous. [Found: O(active), 2.52. Calc. for the dehydrated product: O(active), 2.53%]. The compound suffered no further significant loss in weight when heated even up to 110° .

The substance forms dark chocolate-red crystals, sparingly soluble in water, giving a red solution. The aqueous solution is alkaline to litmus ($p_H > 8$) and is quite stable. Appreciable decomposition occurs only on prolonged boiling. In faintly acid solution it hydrolyses, forming a diaquo complex. It remains quite stable at room temperature for several months and gives a violet solution in syrupy phosphoric acid.

Diaquo Manganese^{III} Ethylenedibiguanidinium Sulphate.—A solution of hydroxo-aquo manganese^{III} ethylenedibiguanide (1 g. in 200 c.c. of cold water) was acidified with acetic acid and filtered. To the filtrate (p_H 4) was added a solution of ammonium sulphate (0.8 g. in 5 c.c. of water) dropwise with stirring. Yellow silky crystals separated in quantities. These were filtered by suction on a sintered glass-bed funnel, washed with cold water and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 . Finally the crystals were kept in air to acquire a constant weight; yield nearly quantitative. {Found: Mn, 10.61, 10.62; O(active), 1.54, 1.54; N, 27.26; SO_4 , 27.66; H_2O (by loss at 70°), 10.33. $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}\text{Et}(\text{BigH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 10.63; O(active), 1.55; N, 27.08; SO_4 , 27.86; H_2O , 10.44%}.

The sample, when heated at 80° for 3 hours, lost 13.86% in weight (corresponding to loss of $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$). {Found (for the sample heated at 80°): O(active), 1.78; SO_4 , 32.6. $(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{SO}_4)\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}\text{Et}(\text{BigH})_2 (\text{SO}_4)_{0.5}$ requires O(active), 1.80; SO_4 , 32.36%}.

The substance forms yellow silky crystals, almost insoluble in water. It becomes anhydrous at 70° and loses one molecule of co-ordinated water at 80° without any decomposition.

Diaquo Manganese^{III} Ethylenedibiguanidinium Selenate.—The complex selenate was prepared by adding dropwise a solution of sodium selenate to that of hydroxo-aquo manganese^{III} ethylenedibiguanide (1 g. in 200 c.c. of cold water), acidified with acetic acid. The yellow silky crystals that separated were filtered by suction on a sintered glass-bed funnel, washed with cold water and dried as usual; yield nearly quantitative. {Found: Mn, 9.41; Se, 19.97. $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}\text{Et}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{SeO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 9.35; Se, 20.16%}.

For the estimation of selenium, the complex was dissolved in $3N$ -HCl and heated on the water-bath with hydrazine sulphate. Metallic selenium separating was filtered, washed and dried to a constant weight at 120 - 30° . Manganese was estimated as MnNH_4PO_4 , H_2O in the combined filtrate and washings.

The product forms yellow silky crystals, almost insoluble in water, and does not decompose even on boiling its aqueous suspension. It gives a violet solution in syrupy phosphoric acid as usual.

Diaquo Manganese^{III} Ethylenedibiguanidinium Chromate.—A solution of hydroxo-aquo manganese^{III} ethylenedibiguanide (1 g. in 200 c.c. of cold water) was treated with dilute acetic acid until the p_H was adjusted at 4.0. It was then filtered and the filtrate treated with a dilute solution of potassium chromate with stirring, when brownish yellow silky crystals separated out. These were filtered, washed and dried as

usual. {Found: O (active, total), 6.63. $[(H_2O)_2Mn^{III}Et(BigH)_2](CrO_4)_{1.5} \cdot 2.5H_2O$ requires O (active, total), 6.67%}. The product forms brownish yellow silky crystals, sparingly soluble in water.

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